

1 **Title:** Action Leveraging Evidence to Reduce perinatal mortality and morbidity in sub-Saharan Africa
2 (ALERT): study protocol for a stepped-wedge cluster-randomised trial to improve maternal and
3 newborn health in Benin, Malawi, Tanzania and Uganda

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57 **Abstract**

58 **Background:** Insufficient reductions in maternal and neonatal deaths and stillbirths in the past
59 decade are a deterrence to achieving the Sustainable Development Goal 3. The majority of deaths
60 occur during the intrapartum and immediate postnatal period. Overcoming the knowledge-do-gap to
61 ensure implementation of known evidence-based interventions during this period has the potential
62 to avert at least 2.5 million deaths in mothers and their offspring annually. This paper describes a
63 study protocol for implementing and evaluating a multi-faceted health care system intervention to
64 strengthen the implementation of evidence-based interventions and responsive care during this
65 crucial period.

66 **Methods:** This is a cluster randomised stepped-wedge trial with a nested realist process evaluation
67 across 16 hospitals in Benin, Malawi, Tanzania and Uganda. The ALERT intervention will include four

68 main components: i) end-user participation through narratives of women, families and midwifery
69 providers to ensure co-design of the intervention; ii) competency-based training; iii) quality
70 improvement supported by data from a clinical perinatal e-registry and iv) empowerment and
71 leadership mentoring of maternity unit leaders complemented by district based bi-annual
72 coordination and accountability meetings. The trial's primary outcome is in-facility perinatal
73 (stillbirths and early neonatal) mortality, in which we expect a 25% reduction. A perinatal e-registry
74 will be implemented to monitor the trial. Our nested realist process evaluation will help to
75 understand what works, for whom, and under which conditions. We will apply a gender lens to
76 explore constraints to the provision of evidence-based care by health workers providing maternity
77 services. An economic evaluation will assess the scalability and cost-effectiveness of ALERT
78 intervention.

79 **Discussion:** There is evidence that each of the ALERT intervention components improves health
80 providers' practices and has modest to moderate effects. We aim to test if the innovative packaging,
81 including addressing specific health systems constraints in these settings, will have a synergistic
82 effect and produce more considerable perinatal mortality reductions.

83 **Trial Registration:** Pan African Clinical Trial Registry (www.pactr.org): PACTR202006793783148.
84 Registered on 17th June 2020.

85 **Keywords:** Perinatal health, maternal health, intrapartum care, childbirth, respectful maternity care,
86 midwifery, health system intervention, sub-Saharan Africa, hospital

87 **Contributions to the literature**

- 88 • Single component facility-based interventions to improve quality of care have modest to
89 moderate effects. It is unknown if carefully designed, multi-component interventions can
90 lead to greater effects with consistent implementation of evidence-based practices.
- 91 • Within the debate to redesign perinatal care in low- and middle-income countries for quality
92 and equity, our research in hospital settings, how they function and how they can improve

93 processes is of utmost relevance for the global ambition to provide respectful and safe
94 perinatal hospital care for all.

95 • Our intervention design includes end-user participation and applies a health system lens to
96 increase the intervention's relevance to initiate and support effective and context-sensitive
97 processes and sustainable improvements.

98 • We will explicitly merge competency based training and quality improvement into an
99 integrated approach supported by cascade mentoring and leadership training.

100 • New data systems are needed to better understand the drivers of ill-health and mortality.

101 We will test the feasibility of a perinatal e-registry in selected hospitals.

102 **Background**

103 There are two million stillbirths globally, and 2.4 million newborns die before reaching one month of
104 age every year.^{1,2} Almost 300,000 women die during pregnancy and childbirth annually.³ Evidence-
105 based care during the intrapartum period, from the onset of labour to the expulsion of the placenta,
106 carries the greatest lifesaving potential.⁴ The importance to address hypoxic-ischaemic insults
107 causing long-term disabilities or perinatal death is increasingly highlighted.⁵ Moreover, this period
108 provides an opportunity to prevent 800,000 malnutrition-related child deaths annually by initiating
109 breastfeeding.⁶ It is considered a central hub for referral and communication along the continuum of
110 care linking antenatal, postnatal and child health care.⁷

111 Clear evidence-based guidelines for the provision of routine and emergency care during the
112 intrapartum period are established.⁸⁻¹⁰ However, evidence suggests that insufficient provider
113 competencies and substandard professional norms rooted in inadequate pre-service training and
114 malfunctioning processes and operations constrain the implementation of such guidelines for
115 maternal and newborn health.¹¹ Mistreatment of women is also increasingly highlighted as a major
116 challenge during the intrapartum period.¹²

117 Quality improvement (QI) and training are proven to be effective strategies in reducing mortality.^{13,14}
118 A recent study from Uganda and Kenya found that combining training and QI was a successful
119 strategy to achieve more considerable perinatal mortality reductions.¹⁵ Two recent reviews
120 concluded that multi-component strategies addressing several underlying factors related to
121 inadequate care have a larger effect on improving health providers' practices compared to single
122 component strategies.^{16,17} Therefore, there is a need to test the effectiveness and cost-effectiveness
123 of a multi-component intervention. Further, it is critical to understand what can work in different
124 contexts and if it works, why, through assessing acceptability, adoption, appropriateness, and
125 feasibility of an intervention.^{14,18}

126 In response, we propose developing and evaluating a comprehensive and multilevel intervention
127 termed Action Leveraging Evidence to reduce perinatal Mortality and morbidity in sub-Saharan Africa
128 (ALERT). ALERT will focus on intrapartum care and midwifery with a health care system strengthening
129 lens. ALERT specifically targets hospital maternity units and will include i) end-user participation of
130 women, families, and midwifery providers to co-design the intervention; ii) in-service midwifery
131 competency-based training; iii) empowerment and leadership mentoring of maternity unit leaders,
132 and iv) QI in the maternity ward, supported by district-based bi-annual coordination and
133 accountability meetings (Fig. 1).

134 **Figure 1: ALERT Conceptual Framework**

135

136 Our theory of change can be summarised as follows. End-user participation built around narratives of
 137 women, families and midwifery providers is expected to contribute to embed responsiveness and
 138 mutual respect in the training and QI. This should lead to improvements in effective communication,
 139 respect, dignity and emotional support. Together with the training and mentoring, the co-design is
 140 expected to lead to more competent and motivated midwifery providers, thus providing improved
 141 care (e.g., improved foetal monitoring, timely decisions, and emergency and client-centred support
 142 during labour). In addition, immediate breastfeeding, encouraged for all women - including those
 143 experiencing caesarean sections – contributes to improved bonding, nutrition and optimal growth
 144 and development in early childhood. Finally, the QI enhances the use of data to make information
 145 systems more actionable. QI and the district coordination and accountability mechanism should
 146 improve resource allocation efficiency (Fig 1).

147 The specific study objectives are:

- 148 1. To assess the ALERT intervention's impact in hospital maternity units on perinatal and maternal
 149 health outcomes, including women's experience of care.

- 150 2. To evaluate the process of implementation of the intervention to understand what works for
151 whom and under what situation.
- 152 3. To conduct a cost-effectiveness analysis of the ALERT intervention.

153 We hypothesise that ALERT will i) reduce in-facility early perinatal mortality; ii) reduce perinatal and
154 maternal morbidity; iii) improve evidence-based practices (immediate breastfeeding, experience of
155 care); iv) strengthen communication links between primary care and hospitals as well as ante-, intra-,
156 postnatal and child health care; and v) strengthen professional exchange networks through
157 mentoring for sustained learning and action.

158 **Methods: Description**

159 **Study design**

160 We will use a stepped-wedge cluster-randomised design with a nested process evaluation based on
161 realist evaluation¹⁹ to evaluate the process of implementation of ALERT to understand what works
162 for whom and under what conditions.²⁰ We will also conduct a cost-effectiveness analysis to inform
163 scalability. The cluster design was chosen as the intervention will be delivered at the hospital level.
164 Our clusters are defined as a maternity ward of a hospital offering caesarean section and blood
165 transfusion services with a minimum caseload of 2,500 births per year. A stepped-wedge design was
166 chosen to mirror scale-up for policy buy-in and for statistical efficiency as we expect larger cluster-
167 level differences.²¹ In addition, it enables the realist process evaluation and economic evaluation to
168 take place in hospitals where we expect the intervention to be sufficiently mature in the way it is
169 implemented. This protocol follows CONSolidated Standards of Reporting Trials (CONSORT) for
170 stepped-wedge cluster randomised trial (SW-CRT) (Additional file [1](#)) and the Standards for Reporting
171 Implementation Studies (StaRI) (Additional file [2](#)).

172 **Context**

173 ALERT will be implemented in four hospitals in Benin, Malawi, Tanzania and Uganda. These countries
174 were purposely selected to allow for a range of health system characteristics and implementation

175 challenges. While Malawi, Tanzania and Uganda share many health system characteristics (strong
176 public health structures, nurse-midwifery and non-direct entry into midwifery education), there are
177 also distinct differences (Table 1). For example, Malawi and Tanzania have strong task-shifting
178 policies in maternity care whereby mostly non-physician clinicians perform caesarean sections.²² In
179 Uganda and Benin, in contrast, caesarean sections are performed exclusively by medical doctors. In
180 Benin, direct entry into midwifery education is practised and maternity care is thus largely provided
181 by midwives.

182 **Table 1: Characteristics of study countries**

183 **Targeted sites and participants**

184 The trial will commence April 2021 for 30 months (Fig. 2). Trial hospitals were selected purposely to
185 reflect the range of facilities and include typical hospitals currently caring for 30-50% of all births for
186 the respective country.²³ In March 2020, we consulted with national Ministries of Health and
187 prepared a list of all hospitals meeting the selection criteria of i) minimum caseload of 2,500 births
188 per year required based on trial sample size calculation; ii) caesarean section and blood transfusion
189 services available; iii) preferably located in rural districts; and iv) consisting of a mix of typical public
190 but also private-not-for-profit (faith-based) hospitals. We included public and private-not-for-profit
191 hospitals to reflect the typical landscape of hospitals in sub-Saharan Africa and improve our results'
192 generalizability. We then selected four hospitals in each country (Fig. 3).

193 **Figure 2: ALERT intervention implementation schematic**

194

195 Light green indicates the comparison cluster. Dark green indicates the cluster is receiving the intervention. BJ: Benin, MW: Malawi, TZ:

196 Tanzania, UG: Uganda

197 The intervention directly targets health care providers involved in intrapartum care and all women

198 who give birth in the participating hospitals during the study period. In this study, the term

199 'maternity care providers' refers to nurses, nurse-midwives, midwives, auxiliary staff and medically

200 trained staff such as obstetricians working in the maternity ward at one of the study facilities.

201 Women will be eligible if they give birth to a newborn weighing ≥ 1000 grams, which is a proxy for

202 viable gestational age in settings with poor gestational age measurement. Women who gave birth in

203 another location but receive care in the hospital after childbirth will not be included in the study as

204 our intervention targets the intrapartum period.

205 **Figure 3: Map of the ALERT countries with key indicators for the selected study hospitals**

206

207 CS: Caesarean section

208 **The intervention**

209 Intervention development was conceived in response to the SC1-BHC-19-2019 call from the
 210 European Commission to innovate and evaluate interventions to bridge the knowledge-do gap to
 211 improve health during the first 1,000 days of life. Further, our intervention links to the 2030
 212 Sustainable Development Goal agenda²⁴ and the Survive, Thrive, Transform aspirations of the United
 213 Nations.²⁵

214 The ALERT intervention focuses explicitly on the key elements of intrapartum care of i) admission,
 215 labour monitoring; ii) immediate maternal and newborn care; and iii) readiness and care for
 216 complications (Additional file 3). Thus, ALERT will cover all stages of labour, biologically effective
 217 interventions (such as appropriate admission, foetal monitoring, emergency preparedness like
 218 reducing time from decision to perform a caesarean section) and improving experience of care (such
 219 as promoting companionship and communication in the maternity wards).

220 Our intervention is based on previous research in conceptualising and evaluating care QI and training
 221 interventions^{14,26,27} and learning from the large Safe Childbirth Checklist trial in India.²⁸ Key
 222 intervention elements are continuous training and QI based on the assumption that the combination
 223 of these two is needed to address the underlying causes of inconsistent implementation of evidence-
 224 based practices.

225 Further, intervention development and adaptation rely on end-user participation to consider women,
226 families, and health providers' perspectives.²⁹ The design pays attention to the experience of
227 interaction between people and health systems. Understanding health systems responsiveness offers
228 an opportunity to adapt care to changing clients/patients' needs, promote women's access to
229 effective interventions and improve the quality of health services, ultimately leading to better health
230 outcomes.³⁰

231 The intervention will include several training modules based on competency-based methodology and
232 using the Laerdal Global health Mama Birthie low-cost models.³¹ The training will be made available
233 to maternity providers, similar to the successful Helping Mothers and Babies Survive modules.²⁷

234 Mentorship is increasingly recognised as an effective strategy to improve healthcare quality, either as
235 part of QI bundles or as a stand-alone intervention.^{32,33} The ALERT mentoring and leadership training
236 intervention component will use a cascade approach with i) in-facility clinical mentors linked to the
237 QI approach and training; ii) mentorship from in-country ALERT staff for the head of the maternity
238 unit; and iii) mentoring within the international ALERT team. Mentoring will address individual
239 professional attitudes, inter-professional collaboration (teamwork), leadership strengthening for
240 resource negotiations, and other aspects.

241 The QI intervention aims to i) support the consistent implementation of the trainings provided; ii)
242 address operational deficiencies identified during the formative research as part of the end-user
243 participation strategies; and iii) support linkages between established maternal death review teams as
244 well as other hospital improvement structures. We will use standard Plan-Do-Study-Act methodology.
245 Data for follow-up will come from the perinatal e-registry or registers adapted to the type of data.

246 **Implementation strategy**

247 The intervention will be delivered by maternity care providers in the study hospitals and supported
248 by our research teams who are based in national universities and well-placed to deliver training and

249 engage with supporting QI approaches. Local hospital-based training and management resources will
250 be mobilized and integrated. To support the ALERT intervention's institutionalisation and
251 sustainability, there must be strong leadership from the districts and collaboration with the
252 Ministries of Health, training institutions, and integration into existing QI structures in each country.
253 We further linked our training approach to training resources within the countries, thus trainers of
254 trainers as available at national and subnational level.

255 In line with Juran's trilogy and the WHO, we concur that promoting the combination of quality
256 planning, control and improvement allows for more sustainable interventions.³⁴ The QI intervention
257 will be informed by the collaborative QI approach³⁵ and will explicitly link to QI approaches already
258 implemented in the facilities. To bolster knowledge, an adapted QI refresher training will be provided
259 including the PDSA and problem-solving methods. Bottlenecks identified during the health facility
260 assessment, operational deficiencies identified during the ALERT competency-based training
261 sessions, and recommendations arising from the maternal death reviews will be the target of PDSA
262 cycles addressed by the QI team. The hospital-based QI team will be supported by our research team
263 and the head of the maternity unit to develop and implement feasible, small scale solutions.

264 We recognise the barriers described to consistent implementation of QI particularly in resource-poor
265 and understaffed settings.^{14,36,37} PDSA cycles, although widely used, have been associated with
266 limited effects.^{26,38} With this in mind, we plan to make adaptations to the collaborative QI approach
267 in order to increase the effectiveness of the ALERT QI package (see table 2 in additional file 3). By
268 explicitly linking to the existing QI structures including perinatal audit and management, we aim to
269 ease implementation and improve potential scalability.^{39,40} The mentoring approach linking to central
270 national institutions is expected to improve accountability to support the structured and regular
271 implementation of QI and thereby the needed *control* aspect as well as the link to the local
272 management structures. The end-user participation element of the intervention design will allow the

273 incorporation of quality planning which the WHO is now proposing as an essential component of
274 QI.³⁸

275 **Methods: Evaluations**

276 This study includes three evaluations; 1) stepped-wedge trial; 2) realist process evaluation and 3)
277 economic evaluation. The methods for each are described below.

278 **Stepped-wedge trial**

279 **Outcomes**

280 Our primary outcome is in-facility early perinatal mortality defined as in-facility (fresh) stillbirth and
281 24-hour neonatal mortality. Selected secondary and process outcomes are listed in Table 2. For a
282 sub-sample of births, we will use lactate measurement using a simple point-of-care test (Nova
283 Biomedical, StatStrip Xpress-I lactate) to obtain an objective measurement of hypoxic-ischaemic
284 insults to be used in conjunction with the more subjective APGAR score due to interrater differences.
285 It is suggested that lactate provides good predictive values on hypoxic-ischaemic insults as
286 conventional pH measurement and base excess.^{41,42} Breastfeeding initiation will be assessed using
287 information recorded in the perinatal e-registry and women's reports at the time of discharge will be
288 integrated into the exit interviews to determine responsiveness and experience of mistreatment.

289 **Table 2: Primary and secondary outcome indicators**

290 **Method of data collection**

291 The primary and secondary outcome data will be collected through a perinatal e-registry and exit
292 interviews with women being discharged following childbirth. The perinatal e-registry will include
293 standard indicators of pregnancy risks and care received during the antenatal and perinatal period.
294 The indicators were informed by similar clinical data collection in the European Union⁴³ and
295 Tanzania.⁴⁴ We will support standardised admission and follow-up case notes to improve continuous
296 documentation during care provision. After short training sessions facilitated by research staff, data
297 will be entered continuously in the maternity ward by midwifery staff or data clerks (based on

298 country preference). Exit interviews will be administered by research staff every six months during
299 the implementation period (six time points) to 50 randomly selected women who had given birth in
300 each hospital. To assess responsiveness and mistreatment, we will use a recently validated
301 questionnaire with some adaptations.⁴⁵

302 **Data management**

303 The ALERT perinatal e-registry will provide primary and some secondary outcomes and will be
304 implemented in all study hospitals. All women who meet the eligibility criteria will be included. The
305 perinatal e-registry data will be entered on the maternity ward using the Research Electronic Data
306 Capture (REDCap) platform available on tablets or computers.⁴⁶ The programme will have inbuilt
307 ranges and branching logic programmed to improve data quality. Monthly data checking and
308 feedback to providers will also be implemented. Weekly paper-based summary sheets will be used to
309 check data completeness, and double-entry of data for 10% of the records will be done by an
310 external facility supervisor. Supervision structures will include in-hospital supervision by an external
311 resource to the maternity ward and by an ALERT research team data manager.

312 **Sample size**

313 The Hemming et al. formula for stepped-wedge trials was used to calculate the study's power.⁴⁷ We
314 used intra-cluster correlation coefficients for stillbirth and neonatal mortality from a study in Malawi
315 ⁴⁸ and maternal morbidity from a recent trial.⁴⁹ The inclusion of 16 hospitals, each with at least 2,500
316 births per year, will give sufficient power (75-80%) to detect a 25% reduction among in-facility early
317 perinatal mortality with baseline rates between 1.4% to 2.0% and 95%-confidence intervals. We also
318 have sufficient power to assess several secondary outcomes, including maternal morbidity
319 (Additional file 4).

320 **Randomisation**

321 Randomisation will be stratified by country to ensure that hospitals are randomly selected and
322 enrolled in six-monthly steps (four hospitals in four steps) in each country. Randomisation was

323 performed by a statistician, independent from the implementation team, once the hospitals had
324 consented to participate in the study. As with all training and QI interventions, we cannot blind
325 participants (hospitals) to the intervention. However, women and families might not be aware of the
326 exact step in the implementation of ALERT at the hospital where they give birth.

327 **Statistical methods**

328 The statistical analysis will be "intention-to-treat", comparing ALERT intervention clusters (hospital
329 maternity wards) with comparison clusters where care is provided according to national standards.

330 We will define a "transition" period of two weeks during which the intervention is provided and
331 adopted by the respective hospitals.

332 We will use descriptive analysis to review the trends using interrupted time series analysis from the
333 30 months of data collection through the perinatal e-registry.⁵⁰ Seasonal variations will be described
334 (e.g. birth weight and neonatal mortality).^{51,52} While secular declines in stillbirths and early neonatal
335 mortality have been slow in the past; we expect annual declines of at least 2%.⁵³ We will review
336 secular trends over strata (countries) and clusters (hospitals) and estimate the heterogeneity of the
337 effects across clusters as advised by Hemming et al.⁵⁴

338 Considering the limited number of clusters, we will use generalised estimating equations (GEE)
339 adjusting for clusters and for the small sample.⁵⁵ We will adjust for clustering, time-trends and the
340 sequence of inclusion of hospitals⁵⁴ and other methods to perform small-sample adjustments.⁵⁶

341 **Sub-group analysis**

342 Additional sub-group analysis by stratification on select covariates such as birth weight, mode of
343 delivery, time of delivery and type of outcomes will be conducted based on the power and sample
344 size plausibility.

345 **The realist process evaluation**

346 We will assess how the intervention works by assessing how actors take up and implement the
347 intervention components based on mechanisms that are triggered in specific contexts to generate
348 the outcomes. We will analyse the differential effects of interventions in the ALERT settings: why is
349 an intervention successful in one setting but perhaps without effect in another? The evaluation is
350 structured along the realist research cycle,⁵⁷ which starts with the development of an initial
351 programme theory (Fig. 4).

352 **Figure 4: The realist research cycle⁵⁷**

353

354 The initial programme theory will be developed based on the ALERT theory of change, a review of
355 the most current literature and discussions with ALERT researchers. We will adopt a multiple
356 embedded case study design to test the initial theory. In each country, we will select one hospital
357 where the ALERT intervention is implemented at step 1 of the stepped wedge design and a second
358 hospital involved in step 3. This phased recruitment of facilities will enable us to assess how the
359 length of exposure to the intervention and changes over time influence observed outcomes.
360 Selecting two hospitals per country will allow for cross-case comparison and identifying how
361 mechanisms play out differently in different hospital-specific contexts. In each hospital, data will be
362 collected on the implementation of the intervention, the context, the actors and the processes
363 triggered by the intervention through a document review and interviews with (1) hospital managers,

364 heads of maternity, midwives and district directors of health, and (2) mothers and families. We will
365 also draw upon data from other work packages and participatory reflection sessions at ALERT
366 consortium meetings. Audio-recordings will be done on devices which allow data encryption and in
367 case this is not possible, recordings will be immediately transferred to a computer where data can be
368 encrypted. All recordings will be verbatim transcribed and translated to English where needed. All
369 transcripts will be entered in a NVIVO database and pseudo-anonymized to the highest degree
370 possible using identifiers and codes for key variables. The ICAMO heuristic will be used in the data
371 analysis.⁵⁸ The data will first be categorised using the intervention-actor-context-mechanism-
372 outcome configuration. Next, a retroduction approach will be adopted, whereby explanations for the
373 observed outcomes are identified by looking into the mechanisms, actual intervention modalities,
374 actors and context elements. In-case and cross-case analysis will allow for the formulation of the
375 'final' programme theory, which will indicate what it is about the ALERT intervention that works for
376 whom and in which circumstances. This will inform recommendations for scaling up the intervention
377 and tailoring it to different contexts.

378 **The economic evaluation**

379 Closely linked with the realist and effect evaluation will be an economic evaluation of the ALERT
380 intervention. According to Drummond et al., economic evaluation is defined as "the comparative
381 analysis of alternative courses of action in terms of both their costs and consequences".⁵⁹ We
382 propose to evaluate the economic impact of the ALERT intervention by conducting cost-effectiveness
383 analysis, focusing on the mature intervention implemented in step three hospitals. The incremental
384 cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) will focus on the net costs per one reduction in stillbirth and in-facility
385 perinatal mortality. We will utilise the Consolidated Health Economic Evaluation Reporting Standards
386 (CHEERS) to optimise the reporting of our evaluation.⁶⁰

387 **Dissemination**

388 We will follow the European Union's open-access policy and strive to make all ALERT training
389 modules, reports, and scientific articles publicly accessible. We will utilise the following
390 dissemination channels: leaflets, a website (alert.ki.se), workshops and meetings at the local (district)
391 and national level, conference presentations (local, national, and international), and peer-reviewed
392 publications and reports. Key stakeholders, including the study participants (i.e., end-users), Ministry
393 of Health policymakers, and other stakeholders interested in improving maternal and child health will
394 be proactively sought out, and findings from the study shared.

395 **Discussion**

396 **Innovation and potential impact**

397 We will test an innovative multi-component intervention that was carefully conceptualised based on
398 previous research^{13,14}, which will be further refined based on the formative research. The co-design
399 component recognises the need for continuous adaptations of QI, and we believe this is the first QI
400 initiative in this field explicitly integrating formal end-user participation. The ALERT intervention also
401 uses system thinking principles. In several settings across sub-Saharan Africa, interventions and
402 policies to implement (and mainly maintain) the delivery of quality maternity care show inconsistent
403 results. Quality care challenges are increasingly conceptualized as system-related complex problems.
404 Our study applies systems thinking by adopting a theory of change approach and implementing a
405 process evaluation that is based on realist evaluation. It not only starts its empirical research from
406 existing knowledge and theories but will also contribute to develop better theories on implementing
407 QI initiatives in maternal health. Furthermore, the realist process evaluation allows for exploring and
408 assessing the complex causal processes underlying the observed outcomes and identifying the
409 required context factors. In that sense, it demonstrates how theory can be used in the three ways
410 described by Nilsen (2015)⁶¹: (1) to explain how implementation outcomes are shaped, (2) to provide
411 a solid foundation for evaluation of the implementation of interventions and (3) to assess and inform
412 the translation of research findings into policy and practice.

413 High maternal and perinatal mortality rates and the large increases in the proportion of childbirths
414 occurring in health facilities make it paramount to identify and evaluate interventions aimed at
415 reducing mortality during birth, especially since relatively simple, cheap and effective evidence-based
416 interventions are available. While there is good evidence that single component interventions
417 improve health workers' practices and health outcomes, our hypothesis is that our innovative ALERT
418 package will work synergistically and lead to larger and sustainable reduction in in-facility mortality
419 and morbidity. The element of end-user participation explicitly addresses the need to adapt QI to the
420 needs in the settings.¹⁴ Our attention to leadership and mentoring responds to the findings that
421 more holistic approaches are likely to lead to more ownership and sustainable changes.³⁶

422 We will work in hospitals that operate under resource-limited conditions. Too few midwifery
423 providers care for a growing number of women. The lack of professional midwives is increasingly
424 acknowledged globally.⁶² Various pathways in the ALERT intervention aim to strengthen the quality
425 of intrapartum care and midwifery with a view on an enabling environment and improved knowledge
426 management.

427 In recent years, many resources were committed to improving access to facility-based births to
428 achieve the Millennium Development Goal 5 and now the SDGs – with major success.⁶³ In view of
429 these developments, quality of care in these facilities needs to be prioritised. We believe that quality
430 of care and the resources available for maternity care must improve as hospitals care for an ever-
431 increasing proportion of births and emergency referrals. Through stakeholder engagement, we
432 anticipate that during the implementation of ALERT, resources available to hospitals, such as staff
433 allocation, investment in physical infrastructure, medicines and medical supplies and other resources
434 will increase. The leadership mentoring and quality of care improvement components of ALERT might
435 contribute to this increase in resources.

436 Data collection will take place during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic which impacts all kinds of daily life.
437 This raises the need for innovative adjustments in terms of learning resources and training. As our

438 protocol is affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, we are committed to work on resilient solutions for a
439 post-pandemic situation. We will add knowledge to this new situation with appropriate digitalised
440 technologies with regard to communication, teaching and evaluation.

441 Rigorous evaluations of multi-component interventions are needed and will add to the existing body
442 of literature on what combination of components are best suited to improve intrapartum quality of
443 care.¹³ Since ALERT is a multi-faceted intervention, each of the components will have its own set of
444 implementation strengths and challenges. There is a need to contextualize each component and an
445 opportunity to learn from a feasibility and acceptability perspective within a multi-country setting.
446 Highlighting the necessity of measuring what works where and understanding the acceptability of
447 each of the components in the different contexts.

448 **Methodological Considerations**

449 There are some important methodological considerations for the ALERT trial. Additional variables
450 related to COVID-19 were incorporated in the data collection tools after the initial ethics submission
451 and approved by all institutional review boards as an amendment. The intervention development will
452 consider the changed realities of providing care during the COVID-19 pandemic and post-pandemic
453 period.

454 One could argue that the generalisability of the results of the stepped wedge study may be limited
455 due to the small number of health facilities and countries included in the study. Furthermore, there
456 may be some selection bias, as the study hospitals are large high-level hospitals that tend to have
457 more high-risk, complicated pregnancies and births. However, because of its comparative design, its
458 building upon existing evidence and theory, and its attention to context, the realist process
459 evaluation's empirical research will provide insights in the conditions that facilitate or inhibit the
460 ALERT intervention, thus providing relevant information to policymakers in other countries.

461 Neonatal deaths and some important exposure variables such as gestational age are prone to
462 reporting bias as ultrasound in early pregnancy is not routinely used. While we have designed our

463 perinatal e-registry carefully, challenges in completeness and quality of documentation will need to
464 be considered. Exit interviews to assess responsiveness and mistreatment are challenging as women
465 might feel pressured to hide negative feelings and there are social risks in complaining. Differences in
466 reported negative experiences between facility-based and community-based assessments have been
467 reported.⁶⁴ However, funding limitations do not allow us to conduct follow-up visits at home. We will
468 carefully train interviewers to limit the social desirability bias.

469 Stepped-wedge designs are particularly susceptible to secular changes in the main outcome.
470 Therefore, we will allow for a longer assessment period than a traditional parallel-group trial.⁶⁵
471 However, the ALERT trial is implementing an perinatal e-registry to measure the outcome variable
472 continuously, thus minimizing this challenge. We also plan to examine time trends and seasonality
473 and identify the appropriate method to adjust for this. Finally, over the trial 30-month period, other
474 interventions might occur in the hospitals, making it difficult to disentangle the effect of ALERT.

475 We believe our comprehensive evaluation using qualitative and quantitative methods will provide
476 important information on the functioning and effects of QI in typical hospitals in sub-Saharan Africa
477 and will further contribute to the evolving literature on the effects and processes of QI in maternal
478 and new-born care.

479 **Trial status:** Not yet recruiting.

480 **Abbreviations**

ALERT	Action Leveraging Evidence to Reduce perinatal mortality and morbidity
CEA	Cost-effectiveness analysis
ICER	Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio
QI	Quality Improvement
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals

WHO	World Health Organization
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481

482 **Declarations**

483 • **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

484 Written informed consent will be obtained from each study participant. We received ethical
485 approval from the local and national institutional review boards as follows: Karolinska Institute,
486 Sweden (Etikprövningsmyndigheten—Dnr 2020–01587). Makerere University School of Public
487 Health, Higher Degrees, Research and Ethics Committee, Uganda—(HDREC 808). National
488 Institute of Medical Research Tanzania, Tanzania—(NIMR/HQ/R.8a/Vol.IX/3493). Muhimbili
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490 University Ethical Review Committee, Tanzania—(AKU-ERC, EA/2019/044/fb). College of
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493 068/MS/DRFMT/CNERS/SA). The Institutional Review Board at the Institute of Tropical Medicine
494 Antwerp and The Ethics Committee at the University Hospital Antwerp, Belgium—(ITG 1375/20.
495 B3002020000116).

496 • **Consent for publication**

497 Not applicable

498 • **Availability of data and materials**

499 Quantitative datasets will be cleaned and made openly available in an open access online
500 repository (Zenodo - <https://www.zenodo.org/>), after anonymisation alongside with meta-data,
501 to facilitate data sharing and re-use. The training materials created during ALERT, publications,
502 reports will be freely available on the ALERT website and disseminated through the ALERT

503 networks. Qualitative data will not be made available to researchers outside the partner
504 institutions. This decision was approved by the EU and is mainly based on three principles: 1)
505 qualitative data are difficult to interpret or reuse without extensive knowledge of the context
506 and how it was originally collected (i.e. experience and background of the data collector), 2) with
507 the small number of hospitals included in the project it would be difficult to guarantee
508 participants complete anonymity, and 3) the quality of the response may differ if participants
509 knew their spoken word would be made available in an open repository.

510 • **Competing interests**

511 The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

512 • **Funding**

513 This study is part of the ALERT-project which is funded by the European Commission's Horizon
514 2020 (No 847824) under a call for Implementation research for maternal and child health. The
515 contents of this article are solely the responsibility of the authors and do not reflect the views of
516 the European Union.

517 • **Authors' contributions**

518 All authors and members of the ALERT research group participated in developing the project. The
519 first version of this protocol was drafted by KSA with input from JA and CH. CH was responsible
520 for the scientific aspects of the project and the coordination of all work packages. EC and HMA –
521 co-design of the intervention; MG – repositioning midwifery and designing the intervention; JPD,
522 CH, LB, KSA – Overcoming systems and implementation bottlenecks; HK, CH, KSA – perinatal e-
523 Registry; JA and PW – trial design and management; BM and LB – realist process evaluation
524 design; WVD, KSA and LB – developing the economic evaluation. The following co-authors were
525 responsible for adaptation to the corresponding study country: JPD - Benin; EC - Malawi; ABP -
526 Tanzania; PW - Uganda. All authors provided substantive intellectual contributions to the

527 manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript. CH, LB, EC, JPD, MG, HK, ABP,
528 and PW obtained the funding for the project. All authors provided feedback on the manuscript,
529 read and approved the final manuscript.

530 • **Acknowledgements**

531 The ALERT study team is a consortium of researchers and implementers of eight institutions
532 across Europe, Benin, Malawi, Tanzania and Uganda. This group developed the ALERT project and
533 is responsible for implementing and evaluating the multi-faceted intervention. The composition
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792 **Figure Legends**

793 **Figure 1:**

794 **Figure 2:** Light green indicates the comparison cluster. Dark green indicates the cluster is receiving
 795 the intervention. BJ: Benin, MW: Malawi, TZ: Tanzania, UG: Uganda

796 **Figure 3:** CS: Caesarean section

797 **Table 1: Characteristics of study countries**

	Benin	Malawi	Tanzania	Uganda
Country-level indicators				
Estimated population (in 2020, million)	12.1	20.3	62.8	47.2
Maternal mortality ratio per 100,000 live births (2017) ³	397	349	524	375
Neonatal mortality rate per 1,000 live births (2019) ¹	31	20	20	20
Stillbirth rate per 1,000 total births (2019) ²	20.3	16.3	18.8	17.8

% of live births in health facilities #	83.9%	91.4%	62.6%	73.4%
% of facility births in hospitals ##	35.4%	42.2%	47.8%	47.8%
Annual growth rate in % of births in health facilities (most recent DHS compared to survey between 2004-2006 ##	0.7%	2.5%	2.6%	5.8%
% of all live births by CS #	5.1%	6.1%	5.9%	6.2%
- Poorest v Richest wealth quintile	1.6%-12.3%	3.0%-9.1%	2.4%-15.8%	2.7%-14.2%
Among live births in health facilities				
% checked before discharge after facility births ##	81%	57%	51%	47%
% of all live births by CS#	6.1%	6.3%	9.5%	8.3%
Among live births in hospitals				
Neonatal mortality per 1,000 live births ##	32.8	35.8	31.8	27.1
% of newborns breastfed within 1 hour of birth ##	61.8%	73.1%	54.9%	65.3%
Health system indicators				
Doctors /10,000 people population ^	0.8 (2018)	0.4 (2018)	0.1 (2016)	1.7 (2017)
Nursing cadres /10,000 people population^	3.9 (2018)	4.3 (2018)	5.8 (2017)	12.4 (2018)
Predominant midwifery provider ⁶⁶	Midwife	Nurse- midwife	Nurse- midwife	Midwife
Hospital beds / 10,000 people population^	5 (2010)	13 (2011)	7 (2010)	5 (2010)

Current health expenditure per capita (USD PPP, 2018)^	83.2	119.5	112.5	139.3
Out-of-pocket expenditure as % of current health expenditure (201^	45	11	24	38
User fees for childbirth (vaginal/caesarean)^	Official fees	No official	No official	No official

798 CS: caesarean section;

799 # DHS StatCompiler and Survey reports for Demographic and Health Survey data, Benin; 2017-8; Malawi: 2015-16;

800 Tanzania: 2015-16; Uganda: 2016

801 ## Additional analysis of Demographic and Health Survey data, Benin; 2017-8; Malawi: 2015-16; Tanzania: 2015-16;

802 Uganda: 2016

803 ^WHO observer http://apps.who.int/gho/data/node.main.HWFGRP_0020?lang=en

804 **Table 2: Primary and secondary outcome indicators**

Primary outcome indicators	Definition	Methods to obtain outcome
Fresh Stillbirth rate	Number of fresh ^a stillbirths of at least 1000g expressed per 1,000 live and stillbirths	Perinatal e-registry
In-facility early perinatal mortality	Number of fresh stillbirths (as above) and up-to discharge neonatal deaths per 1,000 live and stillbirths (composite indicator)	Perinatal e-registry
Secondary outcomes		
Hypoxic-ischaemic event rate	No of neonates with APGAR <7 at 5 minutes per 1,000 live and stillbirths	Perinatal e-registry
Hypoxic-ischaemic event rate	Umbilical cord lactate of > 5.5 mmol ^b per 1,000 live and stillbirths	Perinatal e-registry, (sub-sample)
Neonatal seizures	No of neonates diagnosed with seizures per 1,000 live and stillbirths	Perinatal e-registry

Caesarean section rate (%)	No of caesarean section per 100 live and stillbirths	Perinatal e-registry
Severe maternal morbidity	No of women with morbidities ^c per 1,000 live and stillbirths	Perinatal e-registry
Responsiveness (%)	Validated questionnaire ⁶⁷ (% score) per 100 live and stillbirths	Survey among women at discharge (exit interviews)
Mistreatment (%)	Proportion of women reporting mistreatment per 100 live and stillbirths	Survey among women at discharge (exit interviews)
Process indicators (selected)		
Detection of foetal distress	No. of detected foetal distress events per 100 deliveries defined by FIGO ⁶⁸	Perinatal e-registry
Decision-to-birth time for caesarean section	Median time (minutes) between decision to do a caesarean section to the birth of the baby	Perinatal e-registry

805 ^aFresh stillbirth is defined a stillbirth that happened during labour at the respective facility, thus where the foetal heartbeat
806 was positive at admission; ^bThe cut-off level may be revised based on data from an ongoing study in Uganda and validation
807 work; ^cSevere maternal morbidity will be defined using pragmatic criteria of major interventions (hysterectomy,
808 laparotomy, blood transfusion, admission to intensive care unit or referral to higher level facility)

809 **Additional file 1: CONSolidated Standards of Reporting Trials (CONSORT) for stepped-wedge cluster**
810 **randomised trial (SW-CRT)**

811 **Additional file 2: Standards for Reporting Implementation Studies (StaRI)**

812 **Additional file 3: ALERT intervention description**

813 **Additional file 4: Sample size calculation (ICC, Inter Cluster Coefficient)**